

THE RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF BEDSORES IN SPINAL CORD INJURED PATIENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17961744>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th December 2025

Accepted: 16th December 2025

Online: 17th December 2025

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies on spinal cord injury patients commonly define pressure ulcers as neurotrophic disorders resulting from spinal cord trauma. This classification underscores the absence of innervation at the site of injury, coupled with the low tissue resistance and their limited capacity for reparative regeneration (Baskov A.B., 2000; Nikitin G.D., Kartashev I.P., 2001; Mikheev E.V., 1998). However, other researchers highlight additional factors such as pressure, shear forces, and friction.

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Materials and methods. This study analyzed the long-term outcomes of inpatient treatment in 12 patients with neurotrophic ulcers caused by post-traumatic spinal cord and vertebral injuries, who had previously undergone unsuccessful conservative and

surgical treatments at other healthcare facilities. These patients received inpatient care in the department of purulent surgery and surgical complications of diabetes at the multidisciplinary clinic of Tashkent Medical Academy from 2020 to 2024. Upon admission, all patients underwent general clinical and instrumental examinations, including MRI of the spine in the area of the wound defect and radiological assessment to rule out osteomyelitis. Along with antibacterial therapy, the patients also received infusion therapy. Among the included patients, 4 (33.3%) were men, and 8 (66.7%) were women. Surgical intervention was performed after preoperative preparation, which included rational antibiotic therapy following bacteriological examination of the wound flora and determining its sensitivity to antimicrobial agents, restoration of the body's electrolyte, water, and protein balance, detoxification, and wound debridement (staged necrosectomies, sanitation with various antiseptics, and the use of polyethylene glycol-based ointments). The main criteria for the readiness of the ulcer for surgery were the presence of granulation tissue across the entire surface, the absence of necrotic tissue, and the lack of clinical signs of wound intoxication.

Results. The analysis of the obtained data showed that the postoperative period proceeded smoothly for all patients, and the wounds healed by primary intention. This outcome can be attributed to the technique we employed, which involves excising the calloused edges of the pressure ulcer, ensuring meticulous hemostasis, and transposing a skin-muscle flap on a broad vascular pedicle, taking into account the vascular architecture. As a result, it was possible to close the pressure ulcers with well-perfused tissue without tension. Additionally, adherence to specific conditions during the postoperative period played a significant role in the successful outcomes.

Conclusion: The priority approach in the treatment of chronic wound defects in patients with lower paraplegia is reconstructive and restorative surgery, which, when a proper strategy is chosen, yields good results. An individually tailored treatment program based on the localization of the wound defect in spinal patients is highly effective in preventing postoperative complications and recurrences. In this regard, "hammer-shaped" and "P-shaped" plastic surgeries for the sacral and hip regions are considered optimal. The primary goal of rehabilitation medicine today is to relieve patients from chronic wound defects, and all surgical interventions aimed at eliminating the pathological focus undoubtedly improve the quality of life for spinal cord injury patients.

List of references:

1. Minasov B.Sh., Valeev M.M., Biktasheva E.M. Surgical treatment tactics and postoperative management of patients with neurotrophic ulcers of the posterior part of the foot based on functional flaps. *Orthopedic Genius*, No. 3, 2016.
2. Nasredinov M.A. Surgical treatment of pressure ulcers in the sacral region in spinal patients, 2002.
3. Sonis A.G., Fomin A.V., Ladonin S.V., Sefedinova M.Yu., Bezrukova M.A., Alexeyev D.G. Modern approach to the treatment of stage IV decubitus ulcers. Volume 5, No. 3 (2020) <https://innoscience.ru/2500-1388/issue/view/2813>.
4. Filatov E.V. Treatment and prevention of pressure ulcers, 2010.